

Master Thesis

MODELLING AND SIMULATION OF HYBRID
WIND- AND PHOTOVOLTAIC CONNECTED
SYSTEM TO NIGERIA POWER NETWORK

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III. List of Formulas

$$\text{Kinetic Energy } KE = 12 \cdot m \cdot v^2 \quad (2.1) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$\text{Power is KE per unit time } P = 12 \cdot \dot{m} \cdot v^2 \quad (2.2) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$\text{Mass flux } \dot{m} = \rho \cdot A \cdot v \quad (2.3) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$dmdt = \rho \cdot A \cdot v \quad (2.4) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$\text{Hence Wind power } P_w = 12 \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^3 \quad (2.5) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$P(v) \approx \begin{cases} 0.4 \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot A \cdot v^3 & v < v_R \\ P_R & \text{for } v > v_R \\ 0 & v > v_{out} \end{cases} \quad (2.6) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$PT = P_w \cdot C_p \quad (2.7) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$PT = 12 \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^3 \cdot C_p \quad (2.8) \dots\dots\dots 24$$

$$E_g; p_v = E_b; p_v \cdot 1 - S_{dir} + E_d; p_v \cdot 1 - S_{diff} + E_r; p_v \quad (2.9) \dots\dots\dots 34$$

$$E_b, p_v = \begin{cases} \frac{E_{b,hor} \cdot \cos^2(\beta, \alpha)}{\sin^2 \gamma_s} & \text{for } \cos^2(\beta, \alpha) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.10) \dots\dots\dots 35$$

$$E_d, p_v = \begin{cases} E_{d,hor} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + \cos(\beta)}{2} \right) & \text{for } \frac{1 + \cos(\beta)}{2} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.11) \dots\dots\dots 35$$

$$E_r, p_v = \begin{cases} E_{g,hor} \cdot \rho_g \cdot \left(\frac{1 - \cos(\beta)}{2} \right) & \text{for } \frac{1 - \cos(\beta)}{2} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.12) \dots\dots\dots 35$$

$$P_{system} = P_{panel} \cdot \text{numpanels} \quad (3.1) \dots\dots\dots 42$$

$$P_{panel} = E_{g,pv} \cdot P_{pk,panel} \cdot \eta_{rel} \cdot \eta_{invESTD} \quad (3.2) \dots\dots\dots 42$$

$$E_{d,hor} = 16 \cdot \gamma_s - 0.4 \cdot \gamma_s \quad (3.3) \dots\dots\dots 44$$

$$T_c = T_a + NOCT - 200.8 \cdot ESTD \cdot 0.01 \cdot E_{g,pv} \quad (3.4) \dots\dots\dots 44$$

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V. List of Abbreviations

PV	Photovoltaic
LVRT	Low Voltage Ride Through
HVRT	High Voltage Ride Through
FRT	Fault Ride Through
SI	Solar Irradiation
NCC	National Control Centre
GW	Gigawatt
MW	Megawatt
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
P&O	Perturb and Observe
IC	Incremental Conductance
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
AM	Air Mass
NERC	Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission
MPP	Maximum Power Point
NDPHC	Niger Delta Power Holding Company
ECN	Electricity Corporation of Nigeria
NDA	Niger Dams Authority
STC	Standard Test Conditions
NEPA	National Electric Power Authority
EPSR	Nigeria Electric Power Sector Reform
PHCN	Power Holding Company of Nigeria
NBET	Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Plc

GENCOs	Generation Companies
TCN	Transmission Company of Nigeria
TSP	Transmission Service Provider
DISCOS	Distribution Companies
IPP	Independent Power Plant
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
NBET	Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Company
KE	Kinetic Energy
DFIG	Doubly Fed Induction Generator
RF	Rectifier
GSC	Grid Side Converter
RSC	Rotor Side Converter
AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct current
mono-c-Si	Monocrystalline
multi-c-Si	Polycrystalline
CIS / CIGS	Copper (indium / gallium) – (selenium / sulphur) compounds
CdTe	cadmium tellurite
LV	Low voltage
HES	Hybrid energy System
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PWM	pulse width modulation
kW	Kilo watt
DNI	Direct (Beam) Normal irradiation

GTI	Global Tilt irradiation
GHI	Global horizontal irradiation
DHI	Diffuse horizontal irradiation
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CPV	Concentrated PV
SHP	Small Hydro Power
VPP	Virtual power plant

VI. List of Symbols

v	wind speed/velocity
\dot{m}	Mass flux
P_w	Wind power
ρ	Air Density
v_R	Rated wind speed
v_{out}	Cut-out wind speed
A	Rotor area
C_p	power coefficient
I_{ex}	exciting current
$\mu c\text{-Si}$	microcrystalline Silicon
γ_s	solar altitude in degrees
T_a	ambient temperature in °C
NOCT	Nominal Operating Cell Temperature in °C
E_{STD}	standard irradiance value of 1000 W/m ²
$E_{g; pv}$	global solar irradiance at the surface on the inclined plane in W/m ²
$E_{b; pv}$	slope direct or beam component in W/m ²
$E_{d; pv}$	slope sky diffuse component in W/m ²
$E_{r; pv}$	slope ground reflected component in W/m ²
S_{dir}	direct Irradiance shading factor, unit-less
S_{diff}	diffuse Irradiance shading factor, unit-less

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Abstract

Electricity is the backbone of modern society and economics. Therefore, economic growth and an increase of social wealth usually led to an increase in demand of electrical energy. Power networks must be adapted to this development. Thereby it must be ensured that any changes in network's topology do not have negative impact on its operation and reliability. That creates a demand of precise models of the corresponding network. Therefore, the goal of this thesis is to propose a hybrid energy system that combines both PV-array and wind turbine in addition to conventional source of electrical energy such as hydro and thermal power generation. A basic control model shall be proposed to determine the optimal locations at which hybrid systems should be erect to ensure maximum exploitation of the available potential under constant change in environmental conditions. The whole hybrid system will be described with comprehensive simulation results which will show the system feasibility. A software simulation model shall be developed in DIgSILENT PowerFactory. And finally, network stability shall be investigated after integration of the proposed hybrid system.

Research Motivation

Over the years, Nigeria power situation has dilapidated. This is because of low generation capacity, inadequate transmission capacity and sometimes shortage of gas. Recently, the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) has provided a good policy towards renewable energy generation. According to the commission, "a minimum of 2,000MW of electricity is targeted to be generated from Renewable energy resources by end of the year 2020". Motivated by this, it calls for research on Photovoltaic and wind energy systems. Which will be the major sources towards actualization of this goal.

Objectives

The main objective of this thesis is to propose a hybrid energy system that combines both PV-array and wind turbine in addition to conventional source of electrical energy such as hydro and thermal power generation. Other objectives are:

- To study and model Photovoltaic Power Plant and wind power park in DIgSILENT PowerFactory.
- To study the characteristic curves and effect of variation of environmental conditions like temperature, wind speed, and irradiation on them.
- To perform a quasi-dynamic analysis on both wind and PV power Module determine the optimal locations at which hybrid systems should be erect to ensure maximum exploitation of the available potential under constant change in environmental conditions.
- Implementation and integrate of the hybrid system into Nigeria Power Network to determine its feasibility and transient stability study will be performed using load event.

1 Introduction

Electricity is the most essential form of energy and a crucial factor for a country to develop economically. Nigeria is a developing country and recently, energy demand is increasing rapidly due to urbanization and industrialization. However, electricity production at present is inadequate for this rapid development. Federal Government of Nigeria in its effort to increase power generation level, incorporated in 2004 the Niger Delta Power Holding Company (NDPHC) [1] [2] as a public sector funded emergency intervention scheme. Despite that the power production is still not enough. Also, most of the existing power plants runs on fossil fuel. Often times, some plants are not in operation due to Gas shortage and technical problems. Therefore, need for Alternative energy generation source. Renewable energy sources such as wind and solar have become significant in the energy transition towards lowering environmental pollution through reduction of emission of toxic gases that lead to the ozone layer depletion. The energy transition in most developed and developing economies is primarily aimed at reducing the reliance on fossil fuels and nuclear energy. The increased interest and rise in demand for clean energy from renewable calls for more installation area for PV power plant and wind turbines.

This thesis presents a study on a grid-connected hybrid wind-photovoltaic power generation system. The model was designed and simulated on the DIgSILENT PowerFactory Software. Hybrid system is better because individual power generation system is not totally reliable. When any of the systems is shutdown, the other can supply power.

1.1 Introduction to Hybrid System

Hybrid as a word has different meanings in renewable energy off-grid systems such as diesel generator/PV-hybrid, wind/diesel generator etc. In this case, 'hybrid systems' refers to Wind turbine and Photovoltaic-array Park integrated into a power generation Network. Wind and solar energy generation capacity has tripled globally since 2009. This is as numerous advocates claims that conventional electric power generation produces greenhouse gas which contributes majorly to global warming. Hybrid generation systems can greatly enhance high load demands at all times. With hybrid system, it is possible to achieve higher generating capacities. Renewable resources for instance solar and wind energy which varies randomly are individually less reliable. Yet, in many regions, when solar and wind resources are combined for power generation, they complement each other by means of daily and seasonal discrepancies. Combination

of these two renewable energy sources could make the power system more reliable, and there will be corresponding costs reduction which still depends on the regional conditions.

Fig. 1.1 : Schematic diagram of a proposed hybrid system [1]

The Schematic diagram of a proposed hybrid system was shown in Fig. 1.1, and it consist of PV and the wind systems. The PV system is powered by the Sun, as the light incident on the PV cells is converted into electrical energy by solar energy harvesting means. The MPPT system extracts the maximum possible power from the PV modules. The ac-dc converter is used to converter ac voltage to dc. Wind turbine, gear box, generator and an ac - dc converter is included in the wind energy system. The wind turbine converts wind energy to rotational mechanical energy and this mechanical energy available at the turbine shaft is in turn converted into electrical energy using a generator.

1.2 Potentials of wind and Photovoltaic Energy in Nigeria

Here the potentials of both wind energy and Photovoltaic energy will be discussed. In addition to that is the various maps indicating the wind speed and solar radiation at different location in Nigeria.

1.2.1 Wind Energy potential

The basic prerequisite for a wind farm planning is finding out the wind potential at the proposed site. This is done by possible recording and evaluating wind measurement at the location. However, wind speed frequency distribution and distribution of wind direction frequency are two representations applied for interpretation of results. Also, in both cases how frequently the wind

direction changes in steps of 1m/s or 10° for wind speed and wind direction respectively. The map of Nigeria showing wind speed measured at altitude of 10metres for different locations [2] can be seen in Fig 1.2.

Fig. 1.2: Map of Nigeria showing wind speed at different locations [3] [2]

1.2.2 Photovoltaic Energy Potential

Nigeria’s proximity to the equator exposes her to significant levels of solar radiation as a result of that there is huge solar energy potential. Fig. 1.3, provides solar Photovoltaic (PV) power generation potential. This map will help in modelling and simulation of PV power plant as one can easily choose a location to study. In this thesis, the decision for location under investigation was made with the help of this map. More details will be seen in the later sections of this report.

SOLAR RESOURCE MAP

PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER POTENTIAL
NIGERIA

This map is published by the World Bank Group, funded by ESMAP, and prepared by Solargis. For more information and terms of use, please visit <http://globalsolaratlas.info>.

Fig. 1.3: Map of Nigeria showing Photovoltaic Energy potential [4]

2 Literature Review

In this chapter a brief review of Nigeria power Sector was done. However, the overview of Hybrid wind and photovoltaic power system, and its main components was presented.

2.1 Nigeria Electrical Power Sector

The historic development of energy supply in Nigeria dates to 1896 [5] when electricity was first generated using 60kw generator in Lagos. Nigerian Electricity Supply Company was established in 1929 as the first electric power utility company. By an Act of Parliament in 1951, the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN) was established, to oversee electricity transmission and distribution. Also, Niger Dams Authority (NDA) was established in 1962 for the development of hydroelectric power generation. For effective operation of power system in ECN and NDA was merged in 1972 to form National Electric Power Authority (NEPA). NEPA was responsible for generation of power, transmission, and distribution of electric power in Nigeria till year 2000. Reform of Nigeria Electricity sector started in the year 2001, due to poor electricity supply in the country. This reform was targeted at establishing an efficient electricity market in Nigeria, and its major objective was transferring management of the infrastructure and assets of the electricity industry to private ownership for sustenance of electricity market in Nigeria. In 2005, the Nigeria Electric Power Sector Reform (EPSR) Act was enacted, and the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) was formed as a body for electricity industry regulation.

Additionally, Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) was established as an interim corporation which comprises of the eighteen successor companies (six generation companies, one transmission company and eleven distribution companies) created from NEPA. Creation of the Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Plc (NBET) [3] was done in 2010, as a credible off-taker of electric power from generation companies. Finally, the privatisation all generation and ten distribution companies were done in November 2013. Transmission company was not privatised, and by November 2014 the last distribution company was privatised as well.

2.1.1 Present Electricity Situation in Nigeria

Current electric power situation in Nigeria was review under three sub-sections. In section one power generation was presented, section two power transmission, and final section presents power distribution.

2.1.1.1 Generation Grid

At present, the total installed generation capacity is about 12.908 GW; with thermal having about 8.4576GW installed capacity. Also, Hydro power plant has about 1.9384GW installed capacity. The privatised Generation companies GENCOs [6] has the installed capacity as shown in Table 2.1. In appendix A-1, the list of all the plant that made up the total installed capacity be seen.

Table 2.1 List of GENCO and its installed capacity with privatisation status [6]

S/N	GENCO	Installed Capacity (MW)	Plant Type	Privatisation Status
1	Afam Power Plc	776	Gas	100% Sold
2	Sapele Power Plc	414	Gas	51% Sold
3	Egbin Power Plc	1020	Gas	100% Sold
4	Ughelli Power Plc	900	Gas	100% Sold
5	Kanji Power Plant	760	Hydro	Long Term Concession
6	Jebba Power Plant	578	Hydro	Long Term Concession
7	Shiroro Power Plant	600	Hydro	Long Term Concession

2.1.1.2 Transmission Grid

Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) is one the companies unbundled from the defunct Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN). It is totally Government owned and manages the electricity transmission network in the country. TCN is responsible transmitting electricity from GENCO to DISCOS. It has about 20,000km [6] transmission lines as can be seen in Fig. 2.1. The voltage levels of Nigeria transmission network are 330kV and 132kV and it can be operated by Transmission Service Provider (TSP).

Fig. 2.1 Nigeria Transmission Grid Map [7]

2.1.1.3 Distribution Grid

After the unbundling of PHCN, eleven electricity distribution companies (DISCOS) were established. **Table 2.2** shows the list of the DISCOS and the states they are covering.

Table 2.2: Nigeria Electricity distribution company and their coverage States [3] [6]

S/N	Name of DISCOS	Coverage states
1	Abuja Distribution Company	FCT, Nassarawa, Kogi and Niger
2	Benin Distribution Company	Delta, Edo, Ekiti, and Ondo
3	Eko Distribution Company	Lagos
4	Enugu Distribution Company	Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi Enugu, and Imo
5	Ibadan Distribution Company	Osun, Ogun, Oyo, and Kwara
6	Ikeja Distribution Company	Lagos
7	Jos Distribution Company	Bauchi, Benue, Gombe, and Plateau
8	Kaduna Distribution Company	Kaduna, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara
9	Kano Distribution Company	Kano, Katsina, and Jigawa
10	Port Harcourt Distribution Company	Rivers, Akwa-ibom, Cross River and Baylesa
11	Yola Distribution Company	Yobe, Borno, Adamawa and Taraba

The DISCOS are completely own by private companies; this is to ensure adequate supply of electricity to consumers.

2.1.2 Nigeria Renewable Energy Sourced Electricity

Nigeria has many renewable energy resources in abundance; some of them are Solar, wind, biomass and small hydro power (SHP). In this report only solar and wind are reviewed. The potentials of wind and solar PV are illustrated in

Fig. 1.2 and Fig. 1.3 respectively. The country's current electrification rate is only 59% and energy demand is expected to grow steadily due to a rapidly growing population and economy. These trends will cause Nigeria to face challenges to meet up with demand in the power sector. Solar PV power plants can play a major role in solving the frequent power failures in Nigeria. The sinking costs for PV systems are helping to make the technology more accessible and viable. The Nigerian government has taken significant steps to improve the standards of regulations for solar power projects. NERC has set a target of generating a minimum of 2,000 MW of electricity from solar PV by the year 2020 and seeks to ensure the following frameworks are fulfilled for solar power companies:

Guaranteed price and access to grid-

- Feed - in - Tariff for Solar, Wind, Biomass & Small Hydro
- Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) based on plant life cycle of 20 years
- Electricity distribution companies (DISCOS) to procure minimum of 1000 MW (50 per cent of the total projected renewable sourced electricity)
- Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Company (NBET) to procure minimum of 1000 MW (50 per cent of the total projected renewable sourced electricity) [8]

If the Federal Government continues to improvement regulatory environment, there is a strong possibility of growth for solar PV businesses in Nigeria. Foreign companies and investors interested in the potential that the sun must increase electrification rates in Nigeria, should explore the Nigerian market in partnership with a local company in Nigeria.

2.2 Wind Power System

Wind power hinge on air speed (velocity) v , air mass(density), and air volume (amount) flowing through the area under study(flux). Just as water pump and windmills turn kinetic energy into

mechanical work, also Modern wind turbines turns kinetic energy of air in motion into electric power.

2.2.1 Basic Equations of wind power

The fundamental equations of wind power [9] are:

$$\text{Kinetic Energy } KE = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m \cdot v^2 \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{Power is KE per unit time } P = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \dot{m} \cdot v^2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{Mass flux } \dot{m} = \frac{dm}{dt} \quad (2.3)$$

From fluid mechanics, mass flow rate is given as (product of density and volume)

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \rho \cdot A \cdot v \quad (2.4)$$

$$\text{Hence Wind power } PW = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^3 \quad (2.5)$$

Power Curve of a wind turbine at different speeds is given by the expression [9]

$$P(v) \approx \begin{cases} 0.4 \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot A \cdot v^3 & v < v_R \\ P_R & \text{for } v > v_R \\ 0 & v > v_{out} \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

Where:

$$P_R = \text{Rated Power } (P_R \approx 0.4 \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot A \cdot v_R^3)$$

v_R = Rated wind speed

v_{out} = Cut-out wind speed

A = Rotor area

ρ = Air density

The total power extracted from the wind resource PT is the product of wind power PW and the power coefficient Cp with value $\frac{16}{27}$ according to Betz Limit.

$$PT = Pw \cdot Cp \quad (2.7)$$

Combing equation 2.5 and 2.7 gives:

$$PT = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot v^3 \cdot Cp \quad (2.8)$$

2.2.2 Wind Turbines

A wind turbine is a machine that converts the energy of the wind to electrical power. It can be classified into two technologies: Fixed speed wind turbine and variable speed wind turbine. The variable speed can further be divided into their generator type: (a) Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) and (b) Fully Rated Converter This project deals with only DFIG wind turbines.

2.2.2.1 Electricity generation from wind turbines

Wind turbines for power generation can be classified according to their application type. Most common applications are:

- Stand-alone operation of wind turbines
- Grid-connected wind turbines and
- Hybrid wind turbines systems, for instance wind-diesel hybrid system or wind-photovoltaic systems.

2.2.2.2 Stand-alone wind turbines

The functionality rules for the operations of wind turbines in stand-alone operation or small insular grids are flexible. This because many devices can run at frequency 47 Hz or 52 Hz with problems. The main problems here are: “What to do with the electrical energy when nobody needs it? Often times, “dead loads” are turned on, which turn the excess power into heat” [10]. Lack of power production is also more problematic: less important loads, for example the washing machine, are turned off by a priority control, and energy storage systems and accumulators are used if available.

Fig. 2.2 : Battery charger, a) Block diagram; CO 1 = Controller for a generator with a field winding excitation, CO 2 = Controller for a permanent-excited generator, b) Load curves of a battery charger [10].

Only hybrid system like a wind-diesel system can save one if there is the no power left on storage systems, and still no available wind. However, the water pump and the battery charger are two most common stand-alone uses of wind turbines. The configuration of battery charger system block diagram and its load curve is shown in Fig. 2.2 above. The rectifier (RF) and load are included in the diagram for behaviour of stationary operation determination. The part labelled A shows that $P_{Load} > P_R$ for the turbine optimum power operation with almost constant excitation. On the hand the part labelled B shows that $P_{Load} < P_R$ for limiting the input power when the battery is fully charged. CO1 and CO2 are Reduction of the exciting current (I_{ex}) and Reduction of operating time (T_o) respectively. Also Fig. 2.3 shows the Wind pumping system operating with variable rotor speeds.

Fig. 2.3 : Wind pumping system operating with variable rotor speeds, (a) Block diagram, (b) Load curve [10]

2.2.2.3 Grid-connected wind turbines

Grid connected wind turbine is very useful due to its ability to feed the produced power it generated into the grid.

Fig. 2.4 : The general structure of grid connected DFIG wind turbine [11]

		Asynchronous generator	Synchronous generator
Direct to the grid, need of reactive power, nearly constant speed	Stall control Without pitch	<p>$n_{max}/n_{sync} = 1 : 1,05$</p>	÷
	Dynamic slip control, with/without pitch	<p>$n_{max}/n_{sync} = 1 : (1,10 - 1,20)$</p>	÷
AC-DC-AC conversion reactive power adjustable variable speed $n_{max}/n_{min} \approx 2:1$	with pitch		
		As above but permanent magnetic excitation	

Fig. 2.5: Types of grid-connected wind turbines [10]

Fig. 2.4 illustrates the general structure of DFIG grid connected system; the power from the wind flows through an area A at a velocity v can be represented mathematically as given in equation 2.5. This wind power is proportional to density of air ρ , cross sectional area A and third power of wind velocity v . However, grid connected wind turbines are of different types as shown in Fig. 2.5 below. They are the direct grid connection which needs reactive power with nearly constant speed. This type is usually asynchronous generator, equipped with stall control without pitch and dynamic slip control with or without pitch. The second type is AC–DC–AC conversion with reactive power adjustable variable speed, it can asynchronous or synchronous generator [12].

2.3 PV Power System

Photovoltaic system is made of Solar cells, Solar modules, solar panels, solar array and solar inverter as shown in Fig. 2.6 used for generation of electricity through photovoltaic effect.

Fig. 2.6: Components of PV system [13]

2.3.1 PV Technologies

There are different PV cell technologies regarding crystal and cell construction. In the PV market, crystalline solar cells are predominant; accounting for about 85% of PV module produced in the world [14]. The two main crystalline solar cells are: monocrystalline (mono-c-Si) and Polycrystalline (multi-c-Si) with high and lower efficiency respectively [14]. PV modules manufacture from the crystalline solar cells are depicted in Fig. 2.7. On the other hand, thin film cells are very cheap, flexible and flexible to use but efficiency is lower; they are: amorphous Silicon (a-Si), microcrystalline Silicon ($\mu\text{c-Si}$), Copper (indium / gallium) - (selenium / sulfur) compounds (CIS / CIGS), and cadmium tellurite (CdTe). Also, organic solar cells and crystalline solar cells with several band distances are new technologies [14].

Fig. 2.7: crystalline based PV-modules

2.3.2 Applications of Photovoltaic Systems

Photovoltaic systems can be applied in two major categories: Stand-alone system and Grid connected systems.

2.3.2.1 Stand-alone systems

Stand-alone application of PV system is mainly for domestic and small non-domestic use. It usually goes with back-up batteries especially for domestic, this is to ensure continues operation when there is no irradiation. Non-domestic application of stand-alone is mainly for water pumping for irrigation and drinking purposes. Moreover, it can be use in telecommunication and navigational aids.

2.3.2.2 Grid connected systems

A grid-connected PV system [15] are connected to the electric utility network as illustrated in the schematic diagram Fig. 2.8. It has two major unit which are power conversion unit and interfacing unit.

Fig. 2.8 : Components of Grid-connected PV system [16]

The grid connected systems are usually ground mounted when supplying above 1MW. This system is connected to medium or low voltage transmission grid and must equipped to satisfy grid Codes. Grid codes are discussed in section 2.4. Since this thesis is centred on grid connected systems, overview of the individual components can be seen the next section.

2.3.2.3 Grid-connected inverters

Inverter is the major technology to get reliable and safety PV system operation for grid interconnection. It is also needed to generate high quality power to ac utility system with affordable

price. To meet these requirements, a recent power electronics-based PV inverters technology are applied. power can be generated through high frequency switching of semiconductor devices equipped with pulse width modulation (PWM) technologies [15], high efficiency conversion with high power factor and low harmonic distortion. The microprocessor-based control circuit accomplishes PV system output power control. However, Fig. 2.9 shows two types of inverters— Line-commutated which can control only on-state time but not off-state time, and Self-commutated which can control both on-state and off-state. Self-commutated inverter can further be split into voltage source and current source inverters. The results obtained from a survey shows that the self-commutated voltage inverter type is used in all inverters with a capacity of 1kW or lower, and up to 100 kW. The current control inverter is also employed more popularly due to its high-power factor, transient current suppression, and a simple control circuits can be obtained [15].

Furthermore, inverter can be configured in four different with PV array as shown in Fig. 2.10.

Fig. 2.9: Classification of inverter type [15]

These configurations are: Central inverter, String inverter, multi-string inverter, and AC module inverter.

Fig. 2.10: Different configuration of PV-System with inverters [16]

2.3.2.4 PV System Grid Transformers

In grid-connected PV systems there are two types of transformers there are always installed. The first one steps up voltage from low voltage bus (LV-AC-Bus) to a medium voltage bus (MV-AC-Bus), the LV-AC-Bus here is 0.4kV while MV-AC-Bus ranges around 20kV and 30kV. The second transformer is basically for stepping up voltage from MV-AC-Bus to High voltage and also perform galvanic isolation for PV power plant from power grid.

2.3.3 Environmental Dependence of PV System

The performance of PV power plant [17] depends mainly on two environmental conditions ambient temperature and solar irradiance (SI). This section gives a brief review of these factors.

2.3.3.1 Solar Irradiance (SI)

Various irradiations are reviewed. Table 2-1 provides the summary Global horizontal irradiation (GHI), Direct (Beam) Normal irradiation (DNI), Diffuse horizontal irradiation (DHI) and Global Tilt irradiation (GTI). Solar Energy availability in Nigeria for Power generation and other application based on Changes in GHI and DNI were compared in below.

Fig. 2.11 : Map of Nigeria comparing GHI and DNI [4]

Table 2.3: Types of irradiation as well as its measurement instruments [18]

Type of irradiation	Description	Application	Measure-ment Instru-ment
<p>Global Horizontal irradiation (GHI)</p>	<p>This is the total amount of radiation received from above by a horizontal surface. This value is made up of direct normal irradiation (DNI) and Diffuse horizontal irradiation (DHI)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Fixed PV installations. >Comparisons with solar data bases to perform MCP (Measure Correlate Predict) evaluations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Pyranometer (horizontal) >Reference cell.
<p>Global Tilted Irradiation (GTI)</p>	<p>The total amount of direct and diffuse radiation received from above by a tilted surface. GTI is an approximate value for the energy yield calculation of fixed installed tilted PV panels.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed PV installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Pyranometer tilted in the same angle as the solar module >Reference cell
<p>Direct Normal irradiation (DNI)</p>	<p>Direct Normal Irradiation is the amount of solar radiation received per unit area by a surface that is always held perpendicular (or normal) to the rays that come in a straight line from the direction of the sun at its current position in the sky.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) >Concentrated PV (CPV) >Fixed PV installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Pyrheliometer installed on a sun tracker >Rotating Shadow band Irradiometer
<p>Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation (DHI)</p>	<p>Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation is the amount of radiation received per unit area by a surface (no subject to any shade or shadow) that does not arrive on a direct path from the sun, but has been scattered by molecules and particles in the atmosphere and comes equally from all directions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Fixed PV installations. >Redundancy calculations of GHI → $GHI = DHI + DNI \cdot \cos(\theta)$ Normally, on a sunny day the insolation is 100% GHI with 20% DHI and 80% $DNI \cdot \cos(\theta)$ (θ) is zenith angle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Pyranometer with shadow ball or shadow ring, installed in a sun tracker >Rotating Shadowband Irradiometer

2.3.3.2 Global Tilt irradiation (GTI)

Mathematical expressions given below can be used Global irradiance on inclined plane as proposed in [19] [20].

$$E_{g;pv} = E_{b;pv} \cdot (1 - S_{dir}) + E_{d;pv} \cdot (1 - S_{diff}) + E_r;pv \quad (2.9)$$

Where:

- $E_g; pv$ is the global solar irradiance at the surface on the inclined plane in W/m^2
- $E_b; pv$ is the slope direct or beam component in W/m^2
- $E_d; pv$ is the slope sky diffuse component in W/m^2
- $E_r; pv$ is the slope ground reflected component in W/m^2
- S_{dir} is the direct Irradiance shading factor, unit-less
- S_{diff} is the diffuse Irradiance shading factor, unit-less

Moreover, direct irradiation element of $E_g; pv$ value can be calculated from equation 2.10 as given [19] [20] and shown below.

$$E_{b, pv} = \begin{cases} \frac{E_{b, hor} \cdot \cos v(\beta, \alpha)}{\sin \gamma_s} & \text{for } \cos v(\beta, \alpha) > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Where:

- $E_{b, hor}$ is the direct (beam) irradiance on a horizontal plane
- $v(\beta, \alpha)$ is the angle of incidence in degrees
- γ_s is the solar altitude in degrees

Also, sky Diffuse irradiance on the inclined plane can be calculated as proposed in [19], as given in the expression below.

$$E_{d, pv} = \begin{cases} E_{d, hor} \cdot \left(\frac{1 + \cos(\beta)}{2}\right) & \text{for } \frac{1 + \cos(\beta)}{2} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

Where:

- β is the surface tilt angle from the horizontal plane in degrees

Finally, the ground reflected irradiation can be computed as given in equation 2.12 below.

$$E_{r, pv} = \begin{cases} E_{g, hor} \cdot \rho_g \cdot \left(\frac{1 - \cos(\beta)}{2}\right) & \text{for } \frac{1 - \cos(\beta)}{2} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.12)$$

Where:

- ρ_g is the ground albedo, unit-less
- β is the surface tilt angle from the horizontal plane in degrees

2.3.4 Ambient Temperature

Temperature increase reduces the voltage of a solar cell which in turn affects the power generated. Fig. 2.12 shows I-V and P-V characteristics of three different temperature variations.

Fig. 2.12 : Effect of variation of temperature [21]

The mathematical equation for calculating average operating cell temperature from ambient temperature is given in equation 3.4.

2.3.5 Maximum Power Point Tracking

Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) system is a device whose application is basically to harness the maximum power from a PV system. MPPT control is totally electronic system that can deliver maximum allowable power by changing the operating point of the modules electrically. It is important to operate PV module at its peak since its overall efficiency is around 14%. MPPT ensures that PV Module produces power at its peak. Several MPPT algorithms has been developed such as: Perturb and observe (P&O) algorithm, IC algorithm, Parasitic capacitance, Voltage based peak power tracking Current Based peak power tracking. P&O are widely used due to its simplicity.

2.4 Grid Codes

The Grid code is a technical document containing procedures and principles [22] that governs the operation, maintenance and development of transmission system. Grid codes usually distinguish traditional power plants, with a synchronous generator directly connected to the grid,

from other types, mostly renewable energy resources. German grid code has been found as a reference code for various studies, since it is the most updated one. Therefore, various requirements for the grid connected PV systems, and wind turbines are discussed in this section. According to the current guidelines PV plants or renewable plants connected to the grid should support the grid to maintain its stability and may also remain connected to the grid during fault.

2.4.1 Grid codes for Wind and other renewables power plants

Many countries around the world have developed grid codes for wind power plants due to high penetration of wind power generation technology. Wind power plants are required to perform like conventional plants in terms of reliability and performance. The major requirements for wind plants are Fault Ride Through (FRT) Capability, and reactive power generation/absorption during fault [16]. The ability of a wind farm or a PV power plant refers to as “Power Park” to withstand a transient voltage dip resulting from a fault in the network without being disconnected from the grid depends on the plant’s capability to ride through system fault while supporting voltage during the deviation. This ability of a power park to remain connected during such voltage dips for some given time without collapsing is referred to as fault ride through (FRT) capability and is presented as voltage (pu) vs time (s) curve.

Fig. 2.13 : Voltage Fault Ride Through requirement for Power Park Modules [22]

Wind farms and other renewable energy plants are therefore designed in such a way that they can satisfy the FRT requirement specified in different countries’ grid codes by ensuring that the

plants can ride through all types of symmetrical and unsymmetrical system faults, as well as faults leading to very low voltage levels. According to Nigeria grid code, the power park must remain connected for voltage changes at the point of common coupling (PCC) [22] in normal operating range as shown in Table 2.4. Also, the power park modules must be designed to withstand voltage dip and peak as per Fig. 2.13. In [22] details of Grid codes for Nigeria power park module were given. However, the voltage levels used in Nigeria network at present is given in Table 2.1 exclusive of 0.4kV which is low voltage. Modelled network was done in accordance with this standard voltage level.

Table 2.4: Nigeria Voltage Control ranges [22]

Voltage Level (kV)	Minimum Voltage kV(pu)	Maximum Voltage kV(pu)
330	280.5(0.85)	346.5(1.05)
132	112.2(0.85)	145.2(1.10)
66	62.04(0.94)	69.96(1.06)
33	31.02(0.94)	34.98(1.06)
11	10.45(0.95)	11.55(1.05)

3 Modelling of Hybrid Power System

Hybrid energy system in this thesis consists of wind turbine and PV array. To select correct model components and subsystems, for the topic: “Modelling and Simulation of Hybrid wind and Photovoltaic Connected system to Nigeria Power Network”. The entire system sizing should be optimal. To start with, individual components should be modelled. Modelling process helps in making decision on the choice of components to used. This is done by identifying and studying characteristics of the selected components. However, designing a perfect model is complex and consumes a lot of time; for an appropriate model, there should be a compromise among accuracy and complexity. The major system components considered in this model are depicted in Block diagram of Fig. 3.1 below. Details of each block will be seen in the following sections. However, the whole model was done using DIgSILENT PowerFactory Simulation Software.

Fig. 3.1 : Block Diagram for Hybrid Wind and Photovoltaic System Connected to Nigeria Power Grid

From Figure 3.1 above, the subsystems are the wind power generator and PV system which are also used as the primary energy source in this configuration. The subsystems are connected in a way to provide power to the Grid even when one source is available and the other diminished. This configuration was chosen bearing in mind that the primary energy of the hybrid system in question is environmental dependent. For power synchronization of DFIG wind turbine and PV system, interfacing unit is employed. The interfacing unit comprise of medium voltage substation, step up transformer, and other power synchronisers.

3.1 Modelling of PV-System in DIgSILENT PowerFactory

In Fig. 3.2, the general model of PV Grid-connected system was presented, and the entire system components was shown clearly. Moreover, this model can be applied for any size of PV array and implemented to simulation circuitry.

Fig. 3.2: Grid connected PV system model [16]

Modelling of PV in DIgSILENT PowerFactory can be done in two different ways. The first one is aggregated (Equivalent) model, and the second is non-aggregated model. Fig. 3.3 shows an illustration of Two PV models in PowerFactory. The aggregated model represented with a single PV system, an equivalent transformer and a line with interconnecting bus bars.

Fig. 3.3: Scheme of Aggregated and Non-aggregated model in PowerFactory

On the other hand, the non-aggregated model here comprises of four units of PV systems with their individual transformers and they are integrated to a bus bar here MV-Non-aggregated.

3.1.1 Basic Data

In this thesis, a 3-phase 0.5MW PV Generator was selected from PV system models available in 2019 version of DIgSILENT PowerFactory.

Fig. 3.4 PV System model template in PowerFactory

The generic PV System model is shown in Fig. 3.4 , and can be modified based on the design specifications like model, technology, ratings etc. The value of active power can be specified in the basic data page if Active Power Input option is selected. Also, active can be calculated automatically if the Solar calculation option is chosen as shown in Fig. 3.5. here the active power value can be affected by many factors such as the solar panel type, the arrangement of the solar array, the local time and date, and optionally irradiance data [19]. The Solar Calculation is discussed in detail in sub-section 3.1.1.2 since one of the objectives of this thesis is to find a point at which the maximum power (active power) can be achieved under constant change in environmental conditions.

Fig. 3.5: Basic Data page for PV System Template

3.1.2 PV System Model Calculation

The solar calculation can be used to calculate the active power output of a single PV System in PowerFactory software. This is usually done when an Engineer is designing PV power plant is to be sited in a particular location. As the active power output of PV System depends on the environmental conditions Such as ambient temperature and irradiance. The PV System output is given in equations 3.1 and 3.2 [19].

$$P_{system} = P_{panel} \cdot num_{panels} \quad (3.1)$$

$$P_{panel} = \frac{E_{g,pv} \cdot P_{pk,panel} \cdot \eta_{rel} \cdot \eta_{inv}}{ESTD} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- P_{panel} is the active power output of the panel in kW
- P_{system} is the single system active power output in kW
- num_{panels} is the number of panels per inverter

- $E_{g,pv}$ is the global irradiance on the plane of the array in W/m^2 .
- E_{STD} is the standard irradiance value of $1000 W/m^2$.
- $P_{pk,panel}$ is the total rated peak power of the solar panel in kW
- η_{rel} is the relative efficiency of the panel, unit-less.
- η_{inv} is the efficiency factor of the inverter, unit-less

3.1.2.1 Models for Irradiation

In PowerFactory, irradiance can be modelled by entering measurement in file in the dynamic model shown in Fig. 3.6 . There are three ways of specifying components for irradiance on the horizontal plane: first is combination of Global and Direct, second is combination of Global and Diffuse, and lastly is combination of Direct and Diffuse. Each of the above-mentioned specified components are associated with different model. The choice of model to be used is dependent on the design Engineer and the available data.

Fig. 3.6: Dynamic model of PV system in PowerFactory

The components of irradiance on the horizontal plane employed in this project is Global + Diffuse. Hourly, monthly and yearly data was gotten from [23] and entered with characteristic object. While the diffuse component was estimated using **Bugler Model** proposed in [19], and given in equation 3.3.

$$E_{d, \text{hor}} = 16 \cdot \sqrt{Y_s} - 0.4 \cdot Y_s \quad (3.3)$$

Where:

- Y_s is the solar altitude in degrees

3.1.2.2 Model for Temperature

In this thesis, the ambient temperature is taken to operate at a value of 20°C as can be modelled using Fig. 3.6. Nevertheless, average module temperature can be calculated from equation.

$$T_c = T_a + \frac{\text{NOCT} - 20}{0.8 \cdot \text{ESTD}} \cdot 0.01 \cdot E_{g; \text{pv}} \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

T_a is the ambient temperature in °C

NOCT is the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature in °C

ESTD is the standard irradiance value of 1000 W/m²

3.2 Modelling of Wind Turbine in DIgSILENT PowerFactory

Just as in the case of PV system, wind turbines can be modelled to get the desired output either by aggregated or non-aggregated manner. Aggregated model was adopted and used in this thesis. DFIG machine is used with rating of 1.5MW,3PH,50Hz; the selected element from DIgSILENT PowerFactory is shown in Fig. 3.7. This model comes with a 20kV medium voltage and 0.69kV transformer which was later changed to suite Nigeria medium voltage of 33kV. Power produced by wind is typically governed by the tip speed ratio (TSR) hence optimum TSR is determined in this method by measuring the wind speed and rotor speed. Optimum TSR of a wind turbine is constant notwithstanding the wind speed in this way maintaining optimum TSR will ensure operation of the turbine at maximum power point [24].

Fig. 3.7: DFIG Model Template in PowerFactory

Fig. 3.8 : DFIG Dynamics Model in DIgSILENT PowerFactory

DFIG model block are show in Fig. 3.8. The mechanics part embodies the conversion of the kinetic energy of the wind, into rotational energy at the generator shaft. It includes the pitch control, the wind turbine and the shaft. The wind turbine block required wind speed input, pitch angle and turbine speed. The blade angle control is for the characteristics of the pitch angle control; it regulates the generated power varying the power coefficient C_p .

3.3 Model for Hybrid Wind and Photovoltaic System Connected to Nigeria Power Grid

In this section, the details of hybrid model for Nigeria case will be treated. Also, the total output of Active power is the summation of Active power output from PV system and Active power output generated from DFIG wind turbines. Some assumptions were made based on the literature review; Dynamic Network Model of the Nigerian Transmission Grid for Investigations on Power System Stability has been Implementation in [25]. The Hybrid model in this case was integrated in the model in [25], as shown in Fig. 3.10 since it was done in PowerFactory software.

3.3.1 PV System Model for Nigeria grid

To model PV power plant in Nigeria to investigate available potential, three locations are used as case study with the location data given in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Location Data of the PV system case study

S/N	Location Name	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude @ 0° Azimuth	Eleva- tion(metre)
1	Sokoto	13.0059°N	5.2476°E	54°	303
2	Enugu	6.4584°N	7.5464°E	60°	152
3	Port-Harcourt	4.8581°N	6.9209°E	62°	14

These data are used in the implementation to determine optimal places for erection of PV systems and wind turbine ensuring maximum exploitation of the available potential under constant change in environmental conditions.

The following assumptions were made:

- The size of PV Systems is the same for the three locations (50MW each).

- The irradiance data was obtained for each location.
- Ambient temperature of 20°C was used for all the locations.
- Standard irradiance of 1000W/m² was used to perform the Load flow analysis.
- PV systems are associated with MPPT
- Transformer parameters are identical for all the locations.
- Nigeria time zone UTC+01:00 was used for all.
- Fixed/stationary Mounting was used for all the sites.
- Tilt angle of 35° was used for all the sites.
- Inverter efficiency factor of 100% is identical for all the locations.
- Other environmental factors such Ground Albedo and shading factors has the same value for all the location.
- Number of parallel inverters 100

The whole system was modelled in PowerFactory simulation software using the data summarized in Table 2.1. A total of 1400 units of solar panel was used and connected as shown in the PV array block depicted in figure with 20 units connected in series and 140 in parallel.

Fig. 3.9 : PV array control Block

The internal characteristics of the PV array is not within the scope of this thesis, only the connections of the PV array are considered.

Table 3.2 : Component data used in the hybrid system

S/N	Parameter Name	Rated Value
1	PV module	0.32kW
2	PowerFactory PV System	0.5MW, 3PH
3	Transformer	A
		B
		C
4	Cable	10km
5	DFIG Machine	1.5MW,3PH
6	Transformer	2.5MVA, 33/0.69kV

3.3.1.1 PV system Output calculation

The expected active power output of the three selected locations can be calculated using equations 3.1 and 3.2.

Case A: PV system active power output

Expected maximum output power from Sokoto site, take irradiance value from measured data in February 2016 at about 11:45 am ($1030\text{W}/\text{m}^2$) and using data given in section 3.3.1, is 52.74MW. See detailed solution in appendix A-8

3.3.2 Wind Turbine Model for Nigeria grid

Wind turbine model for Nigeria in this case has 30MW capacity located at two locations in the Northern part of the country. These two locations were chosen from the wind speed map in Fig. 1.2 and simulation was carried out using wind speed data at 50m height from [26] NASA website. The site data used in the model are summarised in table below.

Table 3.3: Location Data of the wind turbine case study

S/N	Location Name (State)	Latitude	Longitude	Average wind speed @ 50metre	Elevation (metre)
1	Sokoto	13.0059°N	5.2476°E	7.6m/s	303
3	Katsina	12.5139° N	7.6114° E	7.2m/s	492.85

However, DFIG wind turbine model in PowerFactory was used and wind speed data was entered using powerFactory time characteristic data table.

3.3.3 Load Flow Calculation

As a standard, the control system of the converter decides how PV generator should be represented in ideal steady state operation. In this thesis the generator is operated as a PQ Bus, and it is assumed to produce constant active and reactive power. In reality the active power contribution depends on solar irradiance. The modern converter can operate independently within a range of certain reactive power. The implemented load flow for Nigeria transmission grid after integration of the hybrid wind turbine and PV systems can be shown in Fig. 3.10, also the summary of load flow results is shown in Table 3.4 and Table 3.5. Total installed capacity and reactive power demand of the network can be read from the tables.

Fig. 3.10 : Implemented Nigeria Transmission Grid with Integrated Hybrid System

Table 3.4 : Load Flow Calculation Grid Summary

		DIgSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2		Project: Date: 21/09/2019	
Load Flow Calculation				Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence		Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence		No	
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers Yes		Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for		1.00 kVA	
Consider reactive power limits Yes		Nodes		0.10 %	
		Model Equations			
Grid: 330KV Grid		System Stage: 330KV Grid		Study Case: Study Case	
				Annex: / 1	
Grid: 330KV Grid		Summary			
No. of Substations	71	No. of Busbars	71	No. of Terminals	1719
No. of 2-w Trfs.	4	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0	No. of syn. Machines	0
No. of Loads	55	No. of Shunts/Filters	17	No. of SVS	0
Generation	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA		
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA		
Inter Grid Flow	= -10833.71 MW	-4543.49 Mvar			
Load P(U)	= 10222.54 MW	6219.87 Mvar	11966.08 MVA		
Load P(Un)	= 10660.64 MW	6481.60 Mvar	12476.40 MVA		
Load P(Un-U)	= 438.10 MW	261.74 Mvar			
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA		
Grid Losses	= 611.17 MW	-1169.70 Mvar			
Line Charging	=	-5104.05 Mvar			
Compensation ind.	=	297.46 Mvar			
Compensation cap.	=	-804.14 Mvar			
Installed Capacity	= 0.00 MW				
Spinning Reserve	= 0.00 MW				
Total Power Factor:					
Generation	= 0.00 [-]				
Load/Motor	= 0.85 / 0.00 [-]				
Inter Grid Flow to					
330kV Extension	= -10795.04 MW	-4546.55 Mvar			
HES	= -38.67 MW	3.07 Mvar			
Total	= -10833.71 MW	-4543.49 Mvar			

Table 3.5 : Load Flow Calculation Grid Summary continuation

		DIgSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2		Project: Date: 21/09/2019	
Load Flow Calculation				Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence		Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence		No	
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers		Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for		1.00 kVA	
Consider reactive power limits		Nodes		0.10 %	
		Model Equations			
Grid: 330kV Extension		System Stage: 330kV Extension		Study Case: Study Case	
				Annex: / 2	
Grid: 330kV Extension Summary					
No. of Substations	0	No. of Busbars	0	No. of Terminals	107
No. of 2-w Trfs.	101	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0	No. of syn. Machines	101
No. of Loads	0	No. of Shunts/Filters	0	No. of asyn.Machines	0
No. of SVS					0
Generation	= 10795.04 MW	4730.32 Mvar		11785.96 MVA	
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Inter Grid Flow	= 10795.04 MW	4546.55 Mvar			
Load P(U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Load P(Un)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Load P(Un-U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar			
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Grid Losses	= 0.00 MW	183.77 Mvar			
Line Charging	=	0.00 Mvar			
Compensation ind.	=	0.00 Mvar			
Compensation cap.	=	0.00 Mvar			
Installed Capacity	= 22981.14 MW				
Spinning Reserve	= 12186.10 MW				
Total Power Factor:					
Generation	= 0.92 [-]				
Load/Motor	= 0.00 / 0.00 [-]				
Inter Grid Flow to 330KV Grid	= 10795.04 MW	4546.55 Mvar			
Total	= 10795.04 MW	4546.55 Mvar			
		DIgSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2		Project: Date: 21/09/2019	
Load Flow Calculation				Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence		Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence		No	
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers		Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for		1.00 kVA	
Consider reactive power limits		Nodes		0.10 %	
		Model Equations			
Grid: HES		System Stage: HES		Study Case: Study Case	
				Annex: / 3	
Grid: HES Summary					
No. of Substations	13	No. of Busbars	18	No. of Terminals	156
No. of 2-w Trfs.	14	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0	No. of syn. Machines	0
No. of Loads	4	No. of Shunts/Filters	0	No. of asyn.Machines	2
No. of SVS					0
Generation	= 150.22 MW	72.53 Mvar		166.81 MVA	
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Inter Grid Flow	= 38.67 MW	-3.07 Mvar			
Load P(U)	= 111.48 MW	69.09 Mvar		131.15 MVA	
Load P(Un)	= 116.92 MW	72.46 Mvar		137.56 MVA	
Load P(Un-U)	= 5.44 MW	3.37 Mvar			
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar		0.00 MVA	
Grid Losses	= 0.07 MW	6.51 Mvar			
Line Charging	=	-1.91 Mvar			
Compensation ind.	=	0.00 Mvar			
Compensation cap.	=	0.00 Mvar			
Installed Capacity	= 179.83 MW				
Spinning Reserve	= 0.00 MW				
Total Power Factor:					
Generation	= 0.90 [-]				
Load/Motor	= 0.85 / 0.00 [-]				
Inter Grid Flow to 330KV Grid	= 38.67 MW	-3.07 Mvar			
Total	= 38.67 MW	-3.07 Mvar			

3.4 Virtual power plant

Virtual power plant (VPP) deals with interactions of distributed energy resources, and its major elements are information and communication system [27] [28]. The features of VPP can be compared to conventional power plant because it possesses its own operating cost, generation schedule and generation limits [29]. VPP is very useful to end users because of its environmentally and cost-effective energy supply solution. A model of VPP is shown in Fig. 3.11, it should be noted that VPP is made up of many distributed generation (like wind turbines, PV system micro hydro etc.) interacting with conventional power plants and controlled by a central unit.

Fig. 3.11 : A model of a Virtual Power Plant [28]

3.4.1 Virtual power plant model for Nigeria Network

Virtual Power Plants are used to group generators in the network, in such a way that the total dispatched active power is set to a target value. In powerFactory software, the dispatch of each generator (the Active Power field available in the Dispatch section of the Load Flow page in

the generator element dialog) is scaled according to the Virtual Power Plant rules (must run, merit of order, etc.), to achieve the total target value.

Fig. 3.12: Virtual Power Plant configuration in DIgSILENT

Fig. 3.12 illustrates the VPP for Nigeria case study. It comprises of three dispatchable machines and one non-dispatchable machine. The VPP here was modelled to deliver an active power output of 200MW, with each of the dispatchable machines delivering a minimum of 50MW and max mum of 70MW. This is to ensure constant power supply in the system when the PV power plant is not available.

Furthermore, the plant follows a merit order distribution mode. Merit order 1 is a Hydro power plant installed at Jebba (Jebba 2G1) with capacity of 96.407MW, on the merit order 2 is a steam power plant installed at Sapele (Sapele Steam ST1) with capacity of 120MW and finally merit order 3 is a gap power plant installed at Asco (Asco plant) with capacity of 110MW. Also, the non-dispatchable machine in this case is PV system proposed to be installed in Port-Harcourt

with capacity of 50MW. The test network heatmap colouring is shown in fig 3.13, and the machines with blue colour are contributing to Virtual power plant.

Fig. 3.13 : Virtual power plant modelled network

4 Quasi-Dynamic Simulations of Hybrid PV System and wind Turbine Using Aggregated Model

Electrical engineers are mostly concerned about the performance of electrical systems in the worst-case operational scenarios. The network complexity poses a challenge to intuitively understand which network states and operating conditions causes the problem. Engineer must carry out multiple power-flow simulations with different range of operating scenarios for him to determine the root cause of the problem.

Fig. 4.1 : Expected Output of a Quasi-dynamic simulation [30]

However, this can be achieved by modelling a time dependence network, due to underlying dependence of operational parameter on time. Some of the time dependent electrical problems [30] are:

- Variation of Renewable energy resources for instance wind and solar because of varying wind speed and solar insolation is a function of time.

- Variation of load due to daily and seasonal cycles is also a function of time.
- Equipment ratings vary due to wind and temperature effect.
- Network variations, maintenance outages, faults and unscheduled outages normally have some time dependence.

Load flow variation over time here is not a timescale of seconds like power system transient. The interest is on the behaviour of network over a period of minutes, hourly, days and weeks, or even months/year. Consequently, the kind of output generated for a quasi-dynamic simulation is shown in above.

4.1 Nigeria Network and Simulation Scenarios

The single line diagram of Modelled Hybrid System for Nigeria network before and after performing quasi-dynamic simulation are shown in Fig 4.2 and Fig 4.3 respectively.

Fig. 4.2 : Before quasi-simulation

Fig. 4.3 : After quasi-dynamic simulation

Fig. 4.4 : Quasi-simulation maximum bus voltage profile in p.u

Fig. 4.5 : Quasi-simulation maximum bus voltage profile in p.u continues

4.1.1 Simulation Results

To verify the potential of PV system in Nigeria, three major locations were considered based on the Fig. 1.3. First is Sokoto State in the North representing the high irradiance states, the second is Enugu in the South which also represent States with normal irradiation, and finally Port-Harcourt in the South as well representing the States with low irradiation. These states formed the possible scenarios studied in this thesis.

4.1.1.1 Scenario A: Sokoto State PV-System potential

The following assumptions were made in this scenario:

- The whole PV systems equipped with MPPT.
- Irradiance level varies according to the characteristic input data for one year.
- Ambient temperature remains constant at 20°C

The potential for a period of one year in this location can be seen in Fig 4.6.

Fig. 4.6 : Total active power produced from PV system for period of one year in Sokoto scenario

4.1.1.2 Scenario B: Enugu State PV-System potential

The following assumptions were made in this scenario

- The whole PV systems equipped with MPPT.
- Irradiance level varies according to the characteristic input data for one year.
- Ambient temperature remains constant at 20°C

The potential for a period of one year in this location can be seen in Fig 4.7 Fig. 4.7 : Total active power produced from PV system for period of one year in Enugu scenario

Fig. 4.7 : Total active power produced from PV system for period of one year in Enugu scenario

4.1.1.3 Scenario C: Port-Harcourt PV-System potential

The following assumptions were made in this scenario:

- The whole PV systems equipped with MPPT.
- Irradiance level varies according to the characteristic input data for one year.
- Ambient temperature remains constant at 20°C

The potential for a period of one year in this location can be seen in Fig. 4.8

Fig. 4.8 : Total active power produced from PV system for period of one year in Port-Harcourt scenario

4.1.1.4 Scenario D: Katsina State Wind power potential

The active produce from 15MW DFIG wind turbines under constant change in the wind speed for a period of one was depicted in Fig. 4.9, and it represents the potential in this location. The maximum power of 14.996MW was achieved on 26.01.2016 at 00:00:00 hour

4.1.1.5 Scenario E: Sokoto State Wind power potential

The active produce from 15MW DFIG wind turbines under constant change in the wind speed for a period of one was depicted in Fig. 4.10, and this represent the potential in this location.

Fig. 4.9 : Total active power produced from DFIG wind turbines for period of one-year Katsina scenario

Fig. 4.10 : Total active power produced from DFIG wind turbines for period of one year in Sokoto scenario

5 Results and Analysis

In this Chapter the result from load flow, Virtual power plant and quasi-dynamic simulations and transient stability will be discussed.

5.1 Quai-Dynamic Load Flow Analysis

The purpose of this analysis is to allow power flow analysis of the Nigeria network over a period. In this thesis, three Loads are associated with characteristic as defined in the quasi-dynamic simulation to reflect average daily demand variation, and the variability of wind speed and solar irradiation variation. The results obtained are analysed in this section.

5.1.1 Load profile for maximum PV power plant production

Fig. 5.1 : Total load demand and PV production in scenario A

Fig. 5.2 : Total load demand and PV production in scenario B

Fig. 5.3 : Total load demand and PV production in scenario C

From Fig. 5.1 to Fig. 5.3, different scenarios are presented. In scenario A the active power produced by the PV system covered about 80% of the load. This is because the part of the north under study has low demand for power, and the PV power production is very due to high solar irradiance. Also, in scenario B the PV Power production covered about 33% of the load demand. Finally, in scenario C the active power produced by PV system was able to cover about

16% of the load demand. The reason behind this is lower irradiation value and high-power demand. Because of this, Virtual power plant was introduced in this area to account for the remaining load demand.

5.1.2 Summary Grid results for loading and voltage

Fig. 5.4 : Quasi-dynamic maximum loading result for summary grid

Fig. 5.5 : Quasi-dynamic result for summary grid maximum voltage of all terminals

5.2 Transient Stability Analysis

The purpose of transient stability analysis in this thesis is to investigate dynamic stability of the network for different load flow scenarios. After integration of 180MW from wind turbine and PV park into the network there is need to investigate how the system reacts to such change. Also, it helps to investigate and validate FRT capability condition stated in section 2.4.1 and shown in Fig. 2.13. The result obtained as shown in Fig. 5.6 are voltage magnitude of three selected buses. These are voltages of the buses before load event. And Fig. 5.7 validate the fact that after introduction of load event in network it was able to recover within 0.15 seconds according Nigeria grid code.

Fig. 5.6 : Voltage profile after introduction of hybrid wind- and PV systems

Fig. 5.7 : Voltage magnitude for load event after 20 seconds at NCC Oshogbo

Fig. 5.8 : Voltage magnitude at NCC Oshogbo Load event and no event

In Fig.5.7, load event was introduced at Brin-Kebbi bus bar which triggers after 20 seconds, and its effect was studied at the National control centre (NCC) Oshogbo. In Fig. 5.8 the effect of the fault was compared to the normal operation; the blue line is the normal operation while the green line is the behaviour during fault. There is a voltage dip after the fault with recovers after about 0.15 seconds. This helps to validate the stability of the system.

5.3 Virtual Power Plant Results Discussion

It can clearly be seen from Fig 3.12 that VPP power, initially set on 200MW. The Summary result obtained after simulation is shown in Appendix A-4 to A-6. During the off- peak power production period, renewable will not meet the load demand. The voltage magnitude for quasi-dynamic simulation during VPP operation for two selected buses are shown in Fig. 5.9

Fig. 5.9 : Voltage Profile during VPP operation for NCC and Odukapi L

From the result appendix A-6 the active power interchange is 149.55MW, which shows that the VPP is active.

6 Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

Reduction of greenhouse emissions and global warming is the major drive for growth in renewable energy system, and power generation from renewable energy resources for the past two decades has received numerous attentions globally. In Nigeria not only this environmental concerns that is making the renewable energy to be receiving such enormous attention but to solve power generation and supply problems.

This research has been able to expose the best location for deployment of wind turbine system and PV system. Among the two-hybrid system studied in this thesis, PV system has better performance advantage than Wind power system. As most places in Nigeria has huge potential for PV system unlike wind system that can only perform in some part of the northern Nigeria.

An aggregated model was developed in DIgSILENT PowerFactory using 0.5MVA 3 phase template. Quasi-dynamic simulation was carried for a period of one year to determine the optimal position for hybrid wind and PV systems installation, and to checkmate variation of output power with constant change in solar radiation over the period under study. Transient stability investigation was conducted using load event.

Finally, virtual power plant was introduced into the model to show how the conventional power system can interact with the renewable energy system.

6.2 Recommendation for Future Work

The hybrid PV-wind based systems are increasingly being connected to power networks. Hence further research studies are recommended to develop a non-aggregated model for hybrid PV-wind systems which will account for losses in transmission lines, and PV-system spatial distribution in a large geographical area.

Ambient temperature variation over a period of one year could be used investigate in the next research.

There is also, need for continuous study of Nigeria power Network dynamics especial now that the renewable energy is advancing. There are two major areas for future works in this aspect: Voltage stability as can be seen in this report that after integration of wind turbine and PV systems the bus voltage has a slight voltage dip before normalizing this call for more research

to make it stable. There is also need for research on reactive injection into the network to minimise power losses along the transmission.

There should be more research on the virtual power plant, as this will bridge the gap between load demand and available power production from PV system and wind especially off-peak period in PV case during rainy season.

VII. References

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VIII. Appendix

Appendix A- 1: List of Nigeria installed Generation capacity [25]

Plant Name	Plant Type	Installed capacity (less-De-commissioned units) (MW)
Kainji G.S (Niger)	Hydro Stations	760.00
Jebba G.S (Niger)	Hydro Stations	578.40
Shiroro	Hydro Stations	600.00
Egbin (Lagos)	Thermal Stations	1320.00
Sapele Steam (Delta)	Thermal Stations	720.00
Transcorp Delta II-IV G.S. (Delta)	Thermal Stations	900.00
Afam IV & V (Rivers)	Thermal Stations	351.00
Geregu G.S. (Kogi)	Thermal Stations	414.00
Omotosho G.S.(Ondo)	Thermal Stations	335.00
Olorunsogo (Ogun)	Thermal Stations	335.00
Sapele NIPP (Delta)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	500.00
Alaoji NIPP (Abia)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	500.00
Olorunsogo NIPP (Ogun)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	750.00
Geregu NIPP (Kogi)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	450.00
Omotosho NIPP (Ondo)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	500.00
Ihovbor NIPP (Edo)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	500.00
Odukpani (Cross-River)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	625.00
Gbarain (Bayelsa)	NIPP- Thermal Stations	120.00
Okpai G.S (Delta)	IPP- Thermal Stations	480.00
Afam VI G.S (Rivers)	IPP- Thermal Stations	650.00
Asco G.S (Kogi)	IPP- Thermal Stations	110.00
Ibom G.S (Akwa Ibom)	IPP- Thermal Stations	155.00
AES (Lagos)	IPP- Thermal Stations	294.00
Paras-Energy (Lagos)	IPP- Thermal Stations	72.00
Trans-Amadi (Rivers)	IPP- Thermal Stations	100.00

Rivers IPP (Rivers)	IPP- Thermal Stations	180.00
Azura IPP (Edo)	IPP- Thermal Stations	459.00
Omoku G.S (Rivers)	IPP- Thermal Stations	150.00

Appendix A- 2 : PV module data sheet

	DigSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2	Project:
		Date: 19/09/2019
Grid:	Syst.Stage:	Annex: / 1
AE320M6-72	PV Panel	1 /1
Peak Power (MPP)	320.0000	W
Rated Voltage (MPP)	38.2700	V
Rated Current (MPP)	8.3600	A
Open Circuit Voltage	46.4300	V
Short Circuit Current	9.2600	A
Material	0	
Temperature Coef. (P) NOCT	-0.3600	%/degC degC
Manufacturer	AE Solar	
Characteristic Name	AE320M6-72	
Data source	MAN	
Foreign Key		
Additional Data		
Description	<p>The electrical data apply to standard test conditions (STC): Irradiance of 1000 W/m2 with spectrum AM 1.5 and a cell temperature of 25°C.</p> <p>Filling Factor (%) 74.43 Module Efficiency (%) 16.49 System Voltage (V) 1000 Temp. coefficient Voc (% / °C) -0.36 Temp. coefficient Isc (% / °C) 0.06 Temp. coefficient Pm (% / °C) -0.36 Operating temp. (°C) -40 to +85 NOCT (°C) 45±2</p> <p>TECHNICAL DATA Junction box 3 bypass diodes, IP 67 Wire cross section (Ø, mm²) 4.0 Cable length (mm) 900 or 1100 Connector type MC 4 / MC 4 compatible Dimensions (L x W x H, mm) 1956 x 992 x 40 Weight (kg) 23.5 Specification (mm) Mono 156 / 6 x 12 Hail resistance Max. Ø 28 mm, at 23 m/s Wind load 2400Pa / 244kg / m² Mechanical load 5400Pa / 550kg / m</p>	
Approval Information	<p>Status Not Approved Modified 22/05/2019 13:44:57 Modified by</p>	
Value		
Version		
Change Log		

Appendix A- 3 : Sumary grid voltages and loading profile before VPP

Appendix A- 4 : Load flow summary grid result after VPP introduction

		DigSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2	Project: Date: 01/10/2019
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Load Flow Calculation		Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence		Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence	No
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers	Yes	Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for Nodes	1.00 kVA
Consider reactive power limits	Yes	Model Equations	0.10 %

Grid: 330KV Grid	System Stage: 330KV Grid	Study Case: Study Case	Annex: / 1
Grid: 330KV Grid	Summary		
No. of Substations	71	No. of Busbars	71
No. of 2-w Trfs.	4	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0
No. of Loads	55	No. of Shunts/Filters	17
No. of Terminals	1719	No. of syn. Machines	0
No. of Lines	81	No. of asyn.Machines	0
No. of SVS	0		
Generation	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Inter Grid Flow	= -10842.42 MW	-4446.53 Mvar	
Load P(U)	= 10246.08 MW	6234.19 Mvar	11993.64 MVA
Load P(Un)	= 10660.64 MW	6481.60 Mvar	12476.40 MVA
Load P(Un-U)	= 414.56 MW	247.41 Mvar	
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Grid Losses	= 596.34 MW	-1278.86 Mvar	
Line Charging	=	-5117.40 Mvar	
Compensation ind.	=	297.89 Mvar	
Compensation cap.	=	-806.69 Mvar	
Installed Capacity	= 0.00 MW		
Spinning Reserve	= 0.00 MW		
Total Power Factor:			
Generation	= 0.00 [-]		
Load/Motor	= 0.85 / 0.00 [-]		
Inter Grid Flow to 330kV Extension	= -10692.87 MW	-4463.26 Mvar	
HES	= -149.55 MW	16.73 Mvar	
Total	= -10842.42 MW	-4446.53 Mvar	

Appendix A- 5 : Load flow summary grid result after VPP introduction continuation

		DigSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2	Project: Date: 01/10/2019
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Load Flow Calculation		Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence	Yes	Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence	No
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers	Yes	Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for	1.00 kVA
Consider reactive power limits	Yes	Nodes	0.10 %
		Model Equations	

Grid: 330kV Extension	System Stage: 330kV Extension	Study Case: Study Case	Annex: / 2
Grid: 330kV Extension Summary			
No. of Substations	0	No. of Busbars	0
No. of 2-w Trfs.	101	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0
No. of Loads	0	No. of Shunts/Filters	0
No. of Terminals	106	No. of syn. Machines	101
No. of Lines	0	No. of asyn.Machines	0
No. of SVS	0		
Generation	= 10692.87 MW	4643.91 Mvar	11657.75 MVA
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Inter Grid Flow	= 10692.87 MW	4463.26 Mvar	
Load P(U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Load P(Un)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Load P(Un-U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Grid Losses	= -0.00 MW	180.65 Mvar	
Line Charging	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	
Compensation ind.	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	
Compensation cap.	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	
Installed Capacity	= 22981.14 MW		
Spinning Reserve	= 12151.83 MW		
Total Power Factor:			
Generation	= 0.92 [-]		
Load/Motor	= 0.00 / 0.00 [-]		
Inter Grid Flow to 330KV Grid	= 10692.87 MW	4463.26 Mvar	
Total	= 10692.87 MW	4463.26 Mvar	

Appendix A- 6 : Load flow summary grid result after VPP introduction continuation

		DIGSILENT PowerFactory 2019 SP2	Project:
			Date: 01/10/2019

Load Flow Calculation		Grid Summary	
AC Load Flow, balanced, positive sequence	Yes	Automatic Model Adaptation for Convergence	No
Automatic tap adjustment of transformers	Yes	Max. Acceptable Load Flow Error for	
Consider reactive power limits	Yes	Nodes	1.00 kVA
		Model Equations	0.10 %

Grid: HES	System Stage: HES	Study Case: Study Case	Annex: / 3
Grid: HES Summary			
No. of Substations	13	No. of Busbars	18
No. of 2-w Trfs.	14	No. of 3-w Trfs.	0
No. of Loads	0	No. of Shunts/Filters	0
No. of Terminals	156	No. of syn. Machines	0
No. of Lines	4	No. of asyn.Machines	2
Generation	= 150.22 MW	9.43 Mvar	150.51 MVA
External Infeed	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Inter Grid Flow	= 149.55 MW	-16.73 Mvar	
Load P(U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Load P(Un)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Load P(Un-U)	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	
Motor Load	= 0.00 MW	0.00 Mvar	0.00 MVA
Grid Losses	= 0.67 MW	26.16 Mvar	
Line Charging	=	-1.91 Mvar	
Compensation ind.	=	0.00 Mvar	
Compensation cap.	=	0.00 Mvar	
Installed Capacity	= 179.83 MW		
Spinning Reserve	= 0.00 MW		
Total Power Factor:			
Generation	= 1.00 [-]		
Load/Motor	= 0.00 / 0.00 [-]		
Inter Grid Flow to			
330KV Grid	= 149.55 MW	-16.73 Mvar	
Total	= 149.55 MW	-16.73 Mvar	

Appendix A- 7 : Single Line Diagram of the Nigerian Transmission after introduction of VPP

Appendix A- 8: Detailed solution to problem in section 3.3.1

$$P_{system} = P_{panel} \cdot num_{panels} \quad (6.1)$$

$$P_{panel} = \frac{E_{g,pv} \cdot P_{pk,panel} \cdot \eta_{rel} \cdot \eta_{inv}}{E_{STD}} \quad (6.2)$$

Where:

- P_{panel} is the active power output of the panel in kW
- P_{system} is the single system active power output in kW
- num_{panels} is the number of panels per inverter @ 100
- $E_{g,pv}$ is the global irradiance on the plane of the array in W/m^2 . @ 1030 W/m^2
- E_{STD} is the standard irradiance value of 1000 W/m^2
- $P_{pk,panel}$ is the total rated peak power of the solar panel in kW @ 0.32kW
- η_{rel} is the relative efficiency of the panel, unit-less. @ 100%
- η_{inv} is the efficiency factor of the inverter, unit-less @ 16%

$$P_{panel} = \frac{1030 \cdot 0.32 \cdot 100 \cdot 16}{1000} \approx 527.36kW$$

Applying equation 3.1

$$P_{system} = 527.36 \cdot 100 \approx 52736kW$$

Therefore; $P_{system} \approx 52.74MW$

Statutory Declaration

I declare that I have authored this thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources / resources, and that I have explicitly marked all material which has been quoted either literally or by content from the used sources

Ekene Fidelis Okpara

Name

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Okpara', written over a horizontal line.

Signature